

Social Services for Vulnerable People in the Context of the Russian-Ukrainian War

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the types of social services and the conditions for obtaining them from the public sector of services for the vulnerable population of Ukraine in the context of war. The essence of the state pilot project for the provision of social services to the elderly and persons with disabilities from among internally displaced persons in difficult life circumstances is revealed. The author also presents the legal regulation of the system of social services provision in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. The author substantiates the need for comprehensive promotion of social protection of socially vulnerable categories of citizens during martial law.

Key words

social services, vulnerable population, internally displaced persons.

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Соціальні послуги для вразливої категорії осіб в умовах російсько-української війни

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті описано види соціальних послуг та умови їх отримання від державного сектору послуг для вразливої категорії населення України в умовах війни. Розкрито сутність державного експериментального проекту надання соціальних послуг особам похилого віку, особам з інвалідністю з числа внутрішньо переміщених осіб, які перебувають у складних життєвих обставинах. Також представлено нормативно-правове врегулювання системи надання соціальних послуг в умовах російсько-української війни. Обґрунтовано необхідність всебічного сприяння соціальному захисту соціально вразливих категорій громадян під час воєнного стану.

Ключові слова

соціальні послуги, вразлива категорія населення, внутрішньо переміщені особи.

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Introduction / Вступ

Social problems and their solution are one of the priority areas of Ukraine's state policy. Currently, the social protection system is still being established. The concepts of "vulnerability", "vulnerable groups", "vulnerable situation" are used in many fields of knowledge and have different meanings. They are used by demographers and sociologists, social and medical workers, police and human rights activists, politicians and lawyers, as a rule, to characterise their activities. Social services for the vulnerable category of internally displaced persons can be seen as a certain type of social investment, and if used effectively, they change the very approach to the development of Ukrainian society and contribute to the development of social work in general. Therefore, conducting a realistic assessment of its effectiveness and quality determines the relevance of this study, and in the future will allow to identify priorities and ways to improve both each individual social service and the entire system of social assistance.

Results / Результати

1. Types of social services for the vulnerable category of the population from among the internally displaced persons.

The Cabinet of Ministers has decided to implement a pilot project to provide certain social services to the most vulnerable categories of citizens. These are people who have found themselves in difficult life circumstances due to hostilities or temporary occupation.

The social services will be provided in healthcare facilities under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Social Policy. In particular, these institutions include some sanatoriums in Truskavets and Myrhorod.

The pilot project envisages 4 social services:

- shelter provision;
- supported accommodation;
- inpatient care;
- social adaptation.

These services will be provided free of charge to elderly people and people with disabilities from among the internally displaced persons. Thus, the most vulnerable citizens will be guaranteed not only shelter, but also social support based on individual needs (Government portal, 2023).

From 01 January 2023 to 31 December 2024, a state pilot project to provide social services to the elderly and persons with disabilities from among internally displaced persons in difficult life circumstances is being implemented. The procedure for implementing the project is determined by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 21 March 2023 No. 248. Under the project, social services can be obtained at the State Non-Profit Enterprise Myrhorod Sanatorium "Slava" and the State Non-Profit Enterprise Truskavets Sanatorium "Batkivshchyna".

Both sanatoriums provide the most popular social services:

- supported accommodation
- provision of shelter;
- social adaptation services,

free of charge to internally displaced persons, including:

- the elderly;
- persons with disabilities and persons who moved from the territory of Ukraine temporarily occupied by the Russian Federation, as well as settlements located in the area of military (combat) operations or under temporary occupation, encirclement (blockade), including during mandatory evacuation;

- persons whose housing is destroyed or uninhabitable as a result of damage and who have applied for compensation for the relevant losses.

Within the framework of the project, social services can be obtained at the State Non-Profit Enterprise "Myrhorod Sanatorium "Slava" and the State Non-Profit Enterprise "Truskavets Sanatorium "Batkivshchyna".

Both sanatoriums provide the most popular social services:

- supported accommodation
- provision of shelter;
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- free of charge to internally displaced persons, including: the elderly; persons with disabilities and persons who moved from the territory of Ukraine temporarily occupied by the Russian Federation, as well as settlements located in the area of military (combat) operations or under temporary occupation, encirclement (blockade), including during mandatory evacuation;
- persons whose housing is destroyed or uninhabitable as a result of damage and who have applied for compensation for the relevant losses (Government portal, 2023).

2. Regulatory and legal regulation of the system of social services provision in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war.

The regulatory act that improved the procedure for the provision of social services in times of war is the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 560 of 07 May 2022 (which entered into force on 18 May 2022), which amended the Procedure for the provision of social services to persons with disabilities and elderly persons suffering from mental disorders (hereinafter - Procedure 1), approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 576 of 26 June 2019. No. 576 and to the Procedure for Organising the Provision of Social Services (hereinafter - Procedure 2), approved by the CMU Resolution No. 587 of 1 June 2020 to regulate the provision of social services during the period of the state of emergency and/or martial law.

These bylaws and regulations, in particular:

1) changed the approach to the provision of social services on an emergency (crisis) basis: clause 5-1 of Procedure 1 and clause 34 of Procedure 2 define the grounds for the provision of social services on an emergency (crisis) basis, as well as expand the types of such social services and determine the procedure for their provision. Paragraphs 12, 13, 14 of Procedure 2 establish an approach to determining the needs of the population for social services.

2) the list of subjects of identification of persons with disabilities and elderly persons was expanded: in the first paragraph of clause 6 of Procedure 1 and clause 5 of Procedure 2, volunteers were added to the list of subjects of identification of persons with disabilities and elderly persons;

3) the issue of the procedure for submitting e-documents when applying for social services, including using a mobile application, has been regulated, and the list of documents attached to the application and confirming the status of a person with a disability in need of social services has been expanded, namely, a pension certificate or a certificate for receiving benefits by persons with disabilities who are not entitled to a pension or social assistance issued by a structural unit for social protection of the population of a district, district in Kyiv and Sevastopol

4) the issue of social services provision in case of absence of identity documents and proof of Ukrainian citizenship by a person with disability or an elderly person is regulated: it is envisaged that in case of absence of identity documents and proof of Ukrainian citizenship by a person with disability or an elderly person who needs social services, the decision on social services provision is made without their submission at the request of such person or legal representative or notification of the guardianship and trusteeship authority (for incapacitated persons)

5) the issue of territorial affiliation for recipients of social services has been regulated: if a social manager/social work specialist identifies a person/family belonging to vulnerable categories of the population or influenced by factors that may lead to difficult life circumstances, he/she informs the authorised body or social service provider at the person's declared/registered place of residence (stay) by sending a written or electronic notification no later than the next business day

Thus, the basis for receiving a social service is a decision on the provision of a social service, which is made by a structural unit for social protection of the population or a social service provider in accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Social Services" (2019). The decision to provide such a

social service is made immediately and its provision is ensured within one day. The term of provision of the social service of in-kind assistance is determined individually.

Conclusions / Висновки

During the war, every citizen of Ukraine needs special attention and assistance from both the Government and other organisations in obtaining social services. At this stage, the state stands for the protection of all citizens, regardless of whether they are internally displaced persons or the local population. Identification of people in difficult life circumstances and those in need of external assistance has always been the main task of social assistance agencies. This is especially important during the period of martial law, as a delay can cost lives.

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